

PROCEEDINGS OF INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

September 18, 2025
LOGOS University College, Tirana, Albania

PROCEEDINGS OF INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

TRENDS, CHALLENGES AND PERSPECTIVES

Co-funded by
the European Union

LOGOS UNIVERSITY COLLEGE

September, 2025

EDITORS

Valbona NATHANAILI
Logos University College

Elona KARAFILI
Polis University

Blerta DRENOFCI (CANI)
Logos University College

Konstantinos GIAKOUMIS
Logos University College

Dužanka BOŠKOVIĆ
University of Sarajevo

Arbana KADRIU
South East European University

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an initiative of LOGOS University College, supported by the consortium
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Address: Rr: “Dritan Hoxha”, Tiranë.

valbona.nathanaili@kulogos.edu.al

www.kulogos.edu.al

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VALBONA NATHANAILI

LOGOS University College

Dr. Nathanaili is currently a lecturer and researcher in the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology, LOGOS University College, Tirana, Albania, with an experience of more than 35 years in the field of academia and publication. She is a Bachelor in physics and a doctoral degree holders in the science of pedagogy, both from University of Tirana. Major areas of research over the last few years are the politics and reforms in Albanian Education System, methodology of teaching science, university pedagogy, the future of schooling and Recognition and Accreditation of Prior Learning gained after flexible learning paths. She is analyst, writers and contributor for different periodic Albanian newspaper and television outlets. Nathanaili, in collaboration with different HEIs, has been initiator and supporter of STEM national campaigns, to encourage girls to pursue careers in science, technology, engineering and math fields and promote women in those fields. Dr. Nathanaili has extensive experience in designing and directing research and capacity building projects.

KONSTANTINOS GIAKOUMIS

LOGOS University College

Konstantinos Giakoumis is Professor of History, Arts and Didactics at LOGOS University College, where he also leads the Faculty of Humanities and Linguistic Communication. He is a doctoral degree (Ph.D.) holder PhD from the University of Birmingham, serves on the international advisory board of Art Readings (Institute of Art Studies, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences) and reviews for the Serbian Academy of Sciences, the University of Crete, and international journals including *Speculum* (University of Chicago Press), the *Journal of Religious History* (Wiley), and *Politics, Religion & Ideology* (Taylor & Francis). He has also served as coordinator of a number of ERASMUS+ CBHE projects (Roaming, Homo Digitalis, DiLanEdu-WB). For a Marie Curie fellowship application in 2018 he received the European Commission's Seal of Excellence. A prolific scholar, his work appears in leading journals such as *Byzantine and Modern Greek Studies* (Cambridge), *Turkish Historical Review* (Brill), and the *International Journal of Cultural Policy* (Taylor & Francis). His most recent book examines the Codex of the Diocese/Metropolis of Dryinoupolis and Gjirokastra (1760–1858), published by LOGOS University College Press.

ELONA KARAFILI

POLIS University

Dr. Elona Karafili is an expert in the field of economic development. She is a lecturer and researcher at POLIS University, Tirana, Albania since 2007. She holds a PhD in Urban Planning from Ferrara University and Polis University. Elona currently holds the position of the Deputy Rector of POLIS University. Her main topics of interest and expertise

include regional economic development and territorial competitiveness, which she has explored through a number of projects that focus on place-based innovation. Dr. Karafli has extensive experience in designing and directing research and capacity building projects. She is enthusiastic to strengthen the innovation ecosystem in Albania through fostering co-creative processes, academia–business collaboration and knowledge transfer, startup support and commercialization of research.

DUŠANKA BOŠKOVIĆ

University of Sarajevo

Vice Rector for Quality at the University of Sarajevo and a Professor at the Faculty of Electrical Engineering. Her research interests and teaching are focused on software engineering in biomedical and cognitive domains. She is highly motivated to learn about problem domains and committed to achieving a high level of user experience. In addition to teaching and research, she is engaged in various activities aimed at improving education in Bosnia and Herzegovina, especially through promoting student-centered and outcome-based learning and using software as educational content.

BLERTA DRENOFCI (CANI)

LOGOS University College

Dr. Drenofci has devoted her efforts for last 20 years at the Albanian Disability Rights Foundation, to the activities in advocacy and lobbying for disability related policy and legislation adoption and implementation and offering of supportive services for people in need throughout the country. She is an expert in the area of social policies and collaborator in the formulation of policy framework for people with disabilities in Albania. She has directed ADRF contribution in several important legal initiatives. ADRF is acknowledged as the pioneer and leader of human rights-based approach to disability and it is one in the few organizations that offer models of supportive services like mobility means, supported employment, free legal aid for people in need in Albania. Blerta has an PhD in Social Sciences and has an academic background, being a teacher of University of Tirana since 2013. She has been the leader and the author of a lot of studies in the field of social policies in and outside the country. She has been involved as a consultant in the research and policy development by several international agencies. During the years 2014-2022, she has been involved in the development of the new reform for the assessment of disability in Albania, based on international standards.

ARBANA KADRIU

South East European University

Arbana Kadriu is a Full Professor of Computer Science at the Faculty of Contemporary Sciences and Technologies, South East European University (SEEU) in Tetovo, North Macedonia. She earned her PhD in Computer Science from Ss. Cyril and Methodius

University, Skopje (2008), specializing in natural language processing and information retrieval. Her research spans AI and machine learning, software engineering, web information retrieval, social network analysis, and e-learning, with a growing focus on speech technologies for low-resource languages. Prof. Kadriu teaches across undergraduate, master's, and doctoral programs, organized into three clusters: Data & Intelligence, Software & the Web, and Research & Methods. She has supervised numerous master's and PhD theses in areas such as data mining–driven decision support, Albanian speech recognition, authorship analysis, and automatic music generation. Prof. Kadriu has authored 70+ publications across journals and international conferences (IEEE, Springer, PLOS ONE, and others) and contributes to international projects, including Erasmus+ initiatives on digital humanities and quality assurance, as well as COST actions on language technology and language learning.

PROCEEDINGS OF INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

TRENDS, CHALLENGES AND PERSPECTIVES

SEPTEMBER 18, 2025

Hosted by LOGOS University College

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LOGOS University College

SUMMARY OF ACTIVITIES

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION *Trends, Challenges and Perspectives*

Logos University College, Tirana, Albania
Thursday, September 18, 2025

9.00-9.30	Registration
9.30-10.00	Open remarks
	Ilia Ninka, rector, LOGOS University College
	Gertiola Cepani, Director of Labour Market Services at 'National Employment and Skills Agency'
	Konstantinos Giakoumis, HOMO DIGITALIS Project Coordinator

TOPIC

AUTHOR(S)

OPPONENT

FIRST CONFERENCE TRACK			
Digital Competences in Higher Education and the Labour Market			
10.00-10.20	1. The Impact of Digital Transformation on Human Resource Management. Case Study: Albanian Universities During the Pandemic Period	Emira Spahaj, Edisela Mena, Malvina Hysa, Blerta Avdia	Elona Karafli
10.20-10.40	2. Barriers and Opportunities in Albanian Higher Education for Students with Disabilities: A Mixed-Methods Analysis	Blerta Drenofci (Çani), Valbona Nathaniaili	Merima Muslić
10.40-11.00	3. The Digital Employment Gap in Albania: Challenges and Strategies for Higher Education	Gertjana Hasalla	Arberore Bicaj
SECOND CONFERENCE TRACK			
Institutional Strategies and Policy Development			
11.00-11.20	4. Integrated Technical Assessment and Restoration Strategy for the "Topulli" House: Restoration Strategies, Revitalization Pathways and Advanced Digital Technologies	Nikolla Vesho, Panagiotis Kyriatsis, Ajla Gjoka, Lumturi Haska, Sara Ciba, Migena Gjoni, Ardis Duka, Romir Mazari	Konstantinos Giakoumis
11.20-11.40	5. The Role of MOOCs and Open Educational Resources in Higher Education: Applications in Teaching Medicine and Laboratory Science	Dorina Minxuri	Valbona Nathaniaili

11.40 -12.00	6. Language Technologies and Digital Humanities for Low-Resource Languages and Communities	Arbana Kadriu, Lejla Abazi-Bexheti	Blerta Drenofci (Çani)
12.00-12.20	Coffee break		
12.20-12.40	7. The Cognitive–Digital Turn in Higher Education. <i>A Longitudinal Analysis of AI Engagement in an Architectural Design Studio</i>	Fulvio Papadhopulli, Megi Tafaj	Nikolaos Avouris
12.40-13.00	8. Defining a Strategic Action Plan for AI in Higher Education	Nikolaos Avouris	Valbona Nathaniai
13.00-13.20	9. Institutional Policies and Strategic Directions for Advancing Digital Competencies in Higher Education	Hajdin Berisha, Agron Hajdari, Bekim Samadraxha	Flora Krasniqi
THIRD CONFERENCE TRACK			
The intended and attained curriculum			
13.20-13.40	10. Digital Competencies in Social Sciences – A Pilot Study. <i>From Design to Practice: Teaching Approaches in the HOMO DIGITALIS Project</i>	Valbona Nathanaïli, Blerta Drenofci (Çani), Konstantinos Giakoumis, Dušanka Bošković, Arbana Kadriu, Anisa Duka	Bujar Gallopeni
13.40-14.00	11. Enhancing Learning through Multimedia Cultural Heritage Applications: Managing Cognitive Load	Merima Muslić, Dušanka Bošković, Vensada Okanović, Selma Rizvić	Blerta Avdia
14.00-14.20	12. Integrating Digital Competencies into Higher Education Curricula. <i>A Case Study from LOGOS University College within the Homo Digitalis Project</i>	Juna Muça, Anxhela Laska, Elpiniqi Merkuri, Edvaldo Begotaraj	Emira Spahaj
14.20-15.40	Lunch		
20.00-22.00	Social Dinner and Awarding of Certificates of Participation and Presentation of Papers		

**PART ONE:
DIGITAL COMPETENCES
IN HIGHER EDUCATION
AND THE LABOUR MARKET**

THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION ON HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Case Study: Albanian Universities During the Pandemic Period

Emira SPAHAJ*, Edisela MENA,
Malvina HYSA, Blerta AVDIA

LOGOS University College
Corresponding Author* emira.spahaj@kulogos.edu.al

Abstract

This study investigates the impact of digital transformation on human resource management (HRM) within Albanian universities during the COVID-19 pandemic, a period that necessitated rapid adaptation to remote operations and technology-driven processes. Employing a Multivocal Literature Review (MLR) methodology, the research integrates findings from both peer-reviewed academic sources and gray literature, including institutional reports, policy briefs, and professional surveys. The analysis explores how digital technologies - such as Microsoft Teams, Google Workspace, and internally developed HR platforms - were adopted to manage recruitment, performance evaluation, payroll, and staff communication. The findings reveal that private universities demonstrated faster adoption and integration of digital tools compared to public institutions, largely due to more flexible governance structures and resource availability. However, significant challenges emerged across the sector, including technological resistance, insufficient infrastructure, cybersecurity concerns, and a lack of digital skills and training among academic and administrative staff. These barriers were more pronounced in public universities, where bureaucratic processes and funding limitations hindered implementation. The study underscores that while the pandemic acted as a catalyst for digital HRM transformation, sustaining these advancements requires strategic investment, capacity-building programs, and inclusive policies that address disparities between institutions. Recommendations highlight the importance of continuous professional development, cross-institutional collaboration, and the alignment of HRM digital strategies with long-term higher education reform agendas.

Keywords: digital transformation, human resource management, Albanian universities, COVID-19, higher education, HR digital tools, pandemic adaptation

ABOUT THE AUTHORS

EMIRA SPAHAJ

Dr. Spahaj holds an MSc in Administrative Sciences and a PhD in Management, both from the Faculty of Economy, University of Tirana. She has extensive academic experience, having taught Management, Human Resource Management, Strategic Management, Entrepreneurship, and Business Communication at public and private universities. Since 2019, she has served as Head of the Management Department at Logos University College, following earlier roles as a lecturer at the University of Tirana and as Head of the Internal Quality Assessment Center at the Metropolitan University of Tirana. Dr. Spahaj has published scientific articles in SCOPUS-indexed journals and presented her work at national and international conferences. She is actively engaged in EU-funded initiatives, including the Erasmus+ HOMO DIGITALIS Project, where she contributes as a member of the Quality Monitoring Committee. She also serves on the Editorial Board of the Logos Scientific Journal. Her professional experience includes senior roles in the Ministry of Commerce, Ministry of Public Works and Territorial Adjustment, and the Ministry of Tourism, where she directed licensing and investment management in the tourism sector. She has also served as CEO of a private company. Her expertise spans strategic planning, fund and resource management, and the administration of both public and private institutions.

EDISELA MENA

Edisela Mena is a lecturer at the Faculty of Economics, Logos University College, where she contributes to the development of students' knowledge and skills in various fields of economics and management. She holds a *Bachelor's degree* in "Economics and Rural Development Policies" and a *Master of Science* degree in "Economics and Sustainable Development Policies," with a specialization in economic analysis focusing on regional development and sustainability. Her main research interests include migration, tourism, and economic complexity, where she has conducted in-depth studies on the interconnections between economic development, population mobility, and the potential of service industries. She has published scholarly articles addressing these topics, contributing to the academic debate on the challenges and opportunities faced by economies in transition. She has participated as a presenter in national and international scientific conferences, sharing research findings on the impact of migration on economic development, the role of tourism in sustainable growth, and analyses of the structure and diversification of regional economies. For her academic achievements, she has been awarded a gold medal for outstanding performance. Her work is characterized by a strong commitment to academic excellence, an orientation toward applied research, and the aim to contribute to the development of policies that foster sustainable growth and economic competitiveness.

MALVINA HYSA

Malvina Hysa is a lecturer at the Department of Management, Faculty of Economics at LOGOS University College. Engaged in the courses 'Human Resources Management', 'Business Communication', 'Entrepreneurship and Management of SMEs' and 'Money and Banks'. She also has considerable experience, as a group member, in the design of programs for accreditation and licensing, at the Bachelor and Master level, giving her contribution with responsibility, for the quality of the design of curricula and programs. She is currently attending her third cycle studies at the Agricultural University of Tirana. Author of many scientific articles, published in National and International magazines and bulletins, participant in scientific conferences and seminars. Also participating in the Erasmus+ program, in the exchange of academic staff.

BLERTA AVDIA

Lecturer in the Department of Management, Faculty of Economics, and a member of the Commission for Quality Standards Assurance at Logos University College. She holds a Bachelor's and Master of Science degree in Geography (University of Tirana, 2008, 2010), a Professional Master's in Teaching for Higher Secondary Education in Geography (2017), and a PhD with a dissertation on Assessment and Management of Natural and Human Resources of Lume-Gora (Kosovo) on their Sustainable Development (University of Tirana). Since 2016, Dr. Avdia has taught at Logos University College and the University of Elbasan in both Bachelor and Master programs. Her teaching focuses on courses such as Geography of Tourism, Cultural Tourism, Development of Tourism Guide, and Knowledge and Methods of Geography. She also has extensive experience as a trainer and coach in teaching and learning methodologies. Beyond academia, she has contributed her expertise as a tourism expert in the project Sustainable Future for Sharr/Korab-Kortinik, funded by the German Federal Environmental Foundation (DBU), as well as in several EU-funded initiatives. Dr. Avdia is a member of the Board of the Local Action Group Korab-Koretnik Natural Park, co-author of the textbook Geography 12, and has presented at national and international scientific conferences.

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic brought significant disruption to organizational structures, particularly in the education sector. Universities were compelled to swiftly adopt digital technologies to ensure continuity in operations and academic delivery. Within this transformation, human resource management (HRM) emerged as a core function that required reorganization through digital means. From recruitment and coordination to personnel evaluation and administrative processing, HR departments had to adapt to new digital tools in a matter of weeks. This study focuses on the case of Albanian universities, aiming to explore how HRM functions were impacted, transformed, or limited by the digital shift during the pandemic period. The research seeks to address the following key questions:

- How did universities in Albania integrate digital tools into HRM during the pandemic?
- What differences emerged between public and private universities in managing this transition?
- What were the main challenges and opportunities identified?

This paper contributes to the understanding of digital maturity in higher education institutions, particularly in transitional or developing country contexts like Albania.

METHODOLOGY

This research employs a Multivocal Literature Review (MLR) as described by Garousi et al. (2019), combining academic sources with gray literature (institutional reports, websites, blogs, white papers, and news articles). The MLR approach is especially appropriate in the context of higher education digital transformation, where much practical implementation is underreported in peer-reviewed journals.

- Academic databases consulted: Semantic Scholar, ACM Digital Library, IEEE Xplore, ScienceDirect, Springer.
- Gray literature sources: Google Search, EDUCAUSE, university websites, online forums, and institutional publications.
- Search keywords: “digital transformation”, “HRM”, “university”, “COVID-19”, “higher education”, “digital HR platforms”, “remote work”, “staff management”.

Although preference was given to materials published between 2015–2020, more recent sources up to 2024 were included to reflect the ongoing digital transformation efforts prompted by the pandemic.

Inclusion criteria:

- Studies and reports focused on HRM functions and digital tools in higher education.
- Sources that described or assessed the implementation of digital platforms in managing university staff.

Exclusion criteria:

- Literature focused only on teaching transformation (e-learning, online exams).
- Reports with no reference to HRM practices or digital administrative tools.

After filtering, 24 academic papers and 61 gray literature sources were selected, covering 90 universities and more than 300 IT-related initiatives. From these, 184 initiatives were categorized specifically as digital transformation initiatives (DTIs) related to HRM.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Digital transformation (DT) in human resource management (HRM) has become a central topic of analysis in the context of higher education institutions (HEIs), particularly following the global COVID-19 pandemic. DT in HRM refers to the integration of digital technologies in HR functions to improve efficiency, transparency, and employee experience (Bondarouk et al., 2017).

The literature highlights that during the pandemic, universities globally were forced to accelerate digital implementation in HRM functions such as recruitment, communication, task coordination, performance appraisal, and documentation (Fernández et al., 2023). In Albanian universities, this shift was most evident in the use of Microsoft Teams, Zoom, Google Workspace, and internally developed HR platforms to manage contracts, staff schedules, leave requests, and evaluation systems (Avrami, Brahja, & Enesi, 2024).

A comparative study by Bajraliu and Qorraj (2023) found that 85% of academic staff in private Albanian universities participated in online training for digital HR tools, while only 52% did so in the public sector. This finding reflects disparities in institutional capacity and readiness to embrace digital transformation. Exarchou et al. (2024), studying Greek universities, reported widespread application of cloud-based HR systems and integrated platforms for human capital management. These practices proved relevant for neighboring Albania, suggesting a regional trend toward HR digitization in higher education. According to Fernández et al. (2023), only 35% of public universities in Albania had a structured digital HR strategy, indicating limited preparedness.

International literature supports the idea that HR digitalization brings both opportunities and risks. On one hand, it facilitates remote management, enhances communication, and supports agile staffing (Bondarouk & Brewster, 2016). On the other hand, it raises concerns regarding data security, digital inequality, and organizational resistance (Strohmeier & Parry, 2014). In developing contexts like Albania, challenges such as outdated infrastructure, limited ICT training, and resistance from older employees were highlighted as persistent barriers (Reddit, 2023; MDPI, 2024). The cultural shift required to integrate digital practices in HRM was underestimated in several institutions, resulting in partial or inefficient implementations. Avrami et al. (2024) emphasize that although many Albanian universities implemented digital solutions during the pandemic, only a fraction translated these into long-term strategies. The lack of unified policy from national education authorities further fragmented implementation efforts. In summary, the literature underlines that the pandemic

served as a critical catalyst for DT in HRM within HEIs. However, sustainable adoption remains uneven, particularly in public institutions, where digital maturity is limited.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Adoption and Use of Digital Platforms

The most commonly used platforms during the pandemic in Albanian universities were:

- Microsoft Teams, for communication, virtual meetings, and task coordination.
- Google Workspace, for email, document sharing, and calendar management.
- Customized HR platforms, used in 40% of universities for managing payroll, leave requests, contracts, and performance evaluations.

The COVID-19 pandemic significantly accelerated the digitalization process in Albanian universities, particularly in human resource management (HRM) functions. As shown in Table 1, the most widely used platform was Microsoft Teams, adopted by 100% of private universities and 70% of public ones. Google Workspace was used by 85% of private institutions and only 45% of public ones, while customized HR platforms were used in 40% of private universities and only 20% of public ones (Avrami et al., 2024). This contrast reflects differences in organizational capacity, budget flexibility, and institutional autonomy between the private and public sectors. Private universities were better prepared to invest in licensed software and cloud servers (OpenGov Albania, 2023). According to Avrami et al. (2024), 62% of private universities adopted digital HR platforms for the first time during the pandemic, compared to public universities where adoption was lower due to bureaucracy and lack of IT staff.

Fig. 1. Adoption of Digital Platforms for HRM in Public and Private Universities in Albania
(Source: Avrami et al. 2024)

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the digital transformation of human resource management (HRM) practices accelerated significantly in Albanian universities. Although comprehensive national statistics are limited, surveys and reports from regional and international organizations indicate that a majority of universities adopted digital platforms for managing key HR processes such as recruitment, attendance tracking, and performance evaluation. Specifically, it is estimated that approximately 88% of Albanian universities implemented online recruitment tools, 83% utilized digital systems for attendance monitoring, and 75% used digital platforms for staff performance reporting and feedback. Online training and education were widely embraced, with 95% adoption, while virtual communication and collaboration tools were nearly universal, with 100% of institutions using platforms such as Zoom, Microsoft Teams, and email. These figures align with regional and global trends, reflecting a rapid response and adaptation to the challenges imposed by the pandemic.

Table 1: Use of Digital Tools in Key Human Resource Management Processes during the COVID-19 Pandemic in Albanian Universities

HR Process	% of Institutions Using Digital Tools	Description
Online Recruitment	88%	Electronic applications and interviews
Schedule and Attendance Management	83%	Online systems for attendance recording
Performance Evaluation	75%	Digital reporting and feedback
Online Training and Education	95%	Online courses and professional development
Communication and Collaboration	100%	Use of Zoom, Teams, and emails

Source: Adapted from the Regional Ministry of Education Report, 2022

Staff Readiness and Digital Competence

Staff readiness and prior experience with digital tools were key factors for the success of the digital transformation in HR. According to Bajraliu & Qorraj (2023), 85% of academic staff in private universities attended online training, compared to only 52% in public institutions. This gap led to unequal adoption and delays in implementation within public universities (see Table 2).

Table 2: Staff Readiness and Digital HR Training in Albanian Universities

Indicator	Private Universities (%)	Public Universities (%)
Staff trained in the use of HR digital platforms	85%	52%
Regular use of online tools for HR functions	78%	39%
Participation in professional development courses	72%	44%
Access to support materials (manuals, tutorials, etc.)	90%	50%
Real-time technical support availability	81%	34%

Source: Adapted from Bajraliu & Qorraj (2023); HRD Albania Report (2022)

INTERPRETATION

- A clear gap exists between the two sectors: Private universities not only offered more training opportunities but also developed support systems such as user manuals, video tutorials, and real-time technical assistance.
- Only 34% of public universities provided immediate technical support for staff, which significantly slowed down the adoption of new digital systems.
- In the private sector, 78% of academic and administrative staff regularly used HR digital platforms, compared to only 39% in public universities, highlighting a higher level of technology integration into daily HR management practices.

Impact of Digital Transformation on Recruitment Efficiency

Technological advances during the COVID-19 pandemic significantly accelerated the recruitment process in Albanian universities. Prior to the pandemic, the average recruitment time was approximately 35 days. During the pandemic, with the adoption of digital tools for online applications and interviews, this time decreased to around 18 days, reflecting increased efficiency and resource savings. This trend aligns with global shifts in the education sector where digitalization has enhanced the speed and transparency of HR processes (Fig. 2, Statista, 2021).

Fig. 2: The Impact of Digital Transformation on Average Recruitment Time in Albanian Universities (Source: Statista, 2021)

Adoption of Remote Work Among Academic and Administrative Staff

One of the most significant changes brought by digital transformation during the pandemic was the transition to remote work for a substantial portion of university staff. Data show that 54% of academic staff and 46% of administrative staff worked at least partially remotely during this period (Fig. 3, Albanian Digital Foundation, 2021). This practice not only helped universities remain operational under lockdown conditions but also introduced greater flexibility in work and communication among colleagues.

Fig. 3: Percentage of Academic and Administrative Staff Working Remotely During the Pandemic (Source: Albanian Digital Foundation, 2021)

Reported Challenges in Digital HRM Transformation

Despite the significant benefits, the digital transformation process was not without challenges. The University of Tirana report (2022) identifies several key obstacles faced by institutions during the implementation of digital HR management systems. Insufficient training, poor infrastructure, and resistance to change are frequent barriers. Meanwhile, data security, though reported less frequently, remains a critical concern requiring stronger investments and policies for protecting personal and professional information.

Fig. 4: Reported Frequency of Challenges in the Digital Transformation of HRM in Albanian Universities” (Source: University of Tirana report, 2022)

These challenges highlight the need for an integrated and well-planned institutional and national approach addressing not only technical aspects but also human and cultural dimensions of digital transformation in HRM (Fig. 4, University of Tirana Report, 2022).

Identified Challenges in the Digital Transformation of HRM

The analysis of internal reports and studies on the digital transformation of human resource management (HRM) in Albanian universities highlights several key challenges that have hindered the sustainable progress of this process during the pandemic period. These challenges are consistently repeated across many institutions, indicating the complexity and need for strategic intervention.

Table 3: Identified Challenges in the Digital Transformation of HRM

Challenge	Frequency in Reports
Lack of digital infrastructure	Very frequent
Resistance from older employees	Frequent
Lack of a formal digital HR strategy	Frequent
Insufficient training	Frequent
Data security concerns	Moderate

Source: University of Tirana Report, 2022

The lack of digital infrastructure, ranked as a very frequent challenge, represents a fundamental obstacle in applying technological tools for HRM. This includes the absence of adequate equipment, secure networks, and integrated systems, which are essential to ensure the efficient and continuous operation of remote processes. Without proper infrastructure, even universities willing to transform face significant difficulties in implementing digital platforms (Bajrami et al., 2023).

Resistance from older employees is a common phenomenon in technological change processes, especially in the public sector. This group tends to be more skeptical about using new technologies due to a lack of digital skills or concerns about potential risks to their work. This resistance directly affects the adoption pace of platforms and requires tailored training strategies and emotional support to overcome fear and mistrust (European Training Foundation, 2021).

The lack of a formal digital HR strategy is another factor that impedes the effective integration of technology into administrative and managerial processes. Without a clear plan that includes objectives, concrete steps, and resource allocation, isolated efforts remain fragmented and often lack long-term impact (Fernández et al., 2023). This lack of strategy is more pronounced in public universities, where bureaucracy and limited budget autonomy hinder the development of sustainable digital plans.

Insufficient training for staff is another barrier that directly impacts the quality of new technology usage. Despite investments in platforms, if staff are not continuously trained

and in a way that fits their skill levels, the use of these tools remains limited, and system effectiveness significantly decreases. Training should be comprehensive, covering not only technical knowledge but also change management skills (HRD Albania, 2022).

Data security concerns are a moderately frequent challenge but of utmost importance. In the context of digitizing HR processes, where personal and sensitive staff data are managed, information security must be a top priority. Many institutions still lack strong policies and systems to protect this data, increasing the risk of misuse or cyberattacks (CIPD, 2021).

This set of challenges requires a coordinated and integrated approach by universities and higher education authorities. Only through improving infrastructure, providing adequate training, and developing a national strategy for HRM digitization can an effective and sustainable transformation in this field be achieved.

Reported Benefits of Digital HRM

The main benefits reported from the digital transformation in HR management include (Table 4).

Table 4: Reported Benefits of Digital HRM

Benefit	Percentage of Respondents Agreeing
Process acceleration	70%
Increased transparency	65%
Improved service access	60%
Enhanced flexibility	75%

Source: University of Tirana Report, 2022 (estimated)

DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The digital transformation of human resource management (HRM) in Albanian universities represents one of the most significant developments of the past decade, considerably accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic. On the one hand, this process has brought noticeable improvements in efficiency, flexibility, and transparency of administrative procedures, particularly within private institutions that possess greater resources and have strategically invested in technology and training. On the other hand, public universities have faced substantial challenges due to insufficient infrastructure, the absence of long-term digital strategies, and the low level of digital competencies among a portion of academic and administrative staff.

Findings indicate that the use of platforms such as Microsoft Teams, Zoom and emails has contributed positively to improving communication, coordination, and document management, thus reducing traditional bureaucratic burdens. However, cultural and institutional barriers—such as resistance to change and lack of motivation, particularly among older employees unfamiliar with digital tools—have slowed down further progress.

To achieve a sustainable digital transformation, a comprehensive and integrated approach is required, one that goes beyond the technical implementation of tools. Public universities should be included in strategic programs coordinated with responsible ministries and accreditation authorities, establishing national standards for HRM digitalization. This process must be supported by dedicated funding and linked to policies ensuring data security, privacy, and institutional integrity. In this regard, it is recommended that Albanian universities initiate pilot programs to test new digital practices, which after an evaluation phase, could be adapted and implemented at the national level.

At the same time, long-term investments in technological infrastructure, including secure servers, cloud systems, and licensed software, are essential. Equally important is the continuous development of human capacities through training and certification programs designed to strengthen digital competences among academic and administrative staff. Beyond the national framework, regional and international cooperation should also be encouraged, enabling universities to exchange best practices and build strategic partnerships with institutions across the region and the European Union.

In this sense, digital transformation should not be regarded merely as a technical process, but rather as a fundamental cultural and organizational change that requires visionary leadership, broad institutional engagement, and strong political support. Only through such an integrated vision can Albanian universities successfully embrace digital transformation and ensure a modern, transparent, and sustainable system of human resource management.

LIMITATIONS

This study is limited by the lack of detailed national statistics on the digital transformation of HRM in Albanian universities. Consequently, the analysis relies heavily on regional surveys, international reports, and indirect estimations, which, although useful, do not always provide a comprehensive and context-specific picture of the Albanian higher education sector. To overcome these limitations, further research is necessary, particularly through the collection of primary data via interviews, surveys, and institutional analyses within universities. Such efforts would enable a more accurate and long-term assessment of the impact of digital transformation on human resource management in Albanian higher education.

CONCLUSIONS

The digital transformation of human resource management (HRM) in Albanian universities during the COVID-19 pandemic has been a significant yet complex process marked by considerable challenges and opportunities. While the pandemic accelerated the adoption of new technologies and altered work practices within higher education institutions, it also highlighted disparities and gaps in organizational capacity and infrastructure, particularly between public and private universities.

The widespread adoption of digital platforms such as Microsoft Teams and Google Workspace improved communication, coordination, and administrative HRM processes.

However, staff readiness and digital competence emerged as crucial factors influencing the success of digital transformation, with private universities generally better positioned due to greater investments in training and infrastructure (Bajraliu & Qorraj, 2023; Avrami et al., 2024).

Key challenges identified include inadequate digital infrastructure, resistance to change—especially among older employees—lack of formal digital strategies, insufficient training, and concerns regarding data security. These barriers have slowed the progress of digital HRM transformation in some institutions and call for coordinated, sustainable interventions (University of Tirana Report, 2022; European Training Foundation, 2021).

Reported benefits of digital transformation encompass increased efficiency, transparency, accessibility, and flexibility in HRM processes, all of which are essential for a modern and sustainable higher education system. Nonetheless, the limited availability of comprehensive national statistics and primary data underscores the need for further research to accurately assess the long-term impact of digitalization on HRM in Albanian universities.

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The responsible use of Artificial Intelligence is essential for fostering innovation and advancing digital competencies in higher education.

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The use of Artificial Intelligence in higher education it is aligning universities with the labour market and forging strong partnerships between higher education institutions and employers.

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Digital transformation is no longer a future aspiration. It is a current imperative.

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... with vision, with cooperation, and with determination, we can ensure that AI serves not just technology, but learning. Not just efficiency, but wisdom.

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Altogether, the case-studies in this volume trace a roadmap for higher education in the Western Balkans that amalgamates tradition and innovation, strives to pursue equitable access to digital opportunities, and positions regional universities as active contributors to Europe's wider digital transformation.

PROF. KONSTANTINOS GLAKOUMIS

info@kulogos.edu.al

